

STUDYING ABROAD: WHAT STUDENTS FACE ABROAD

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Abstract. In this article the researcher focused on finding about the student life in abroad. The article defines advantages of studying abroad namely, learning a new languages, boosting the individual resume and experiencing new things and disadvantages including homesickness, high costs and cultural barriers.

Keywords: worldview, out of the country, self-improvement, comfort zone, culture shock, local people , homesick.

Nowadays, the number of the students who has high passion for receiving a qualified education is increasing. In comparison with the past, more and more students are showing high interest in studying at one of the prestigious universities of the foreign countries instead of their homeland. However, receiving a qualified education abroad is not as easy as it is thought. On the one hand, it gives huge opportunities for the young generation, on the other hand it has some drawbacks.

There are a number of advantages of studying abroad. Increasing professional knowledge, increasing the level of knowledge of a foreign language, independence, broadening the worldview, meeting people with different experiences and views are very important for personal and career development. It makes us want to go abroad and study at the universities of our dreams. With moving abroad comes the challenges of settling into a new environment, and it's no wonder it's a little intimidating. Because we do not know what is waiting for us there and we start to have various questions. For instance, “ Can the people of this country accept me? Can I live in this country ? , Are there reliable people and how can I meet them? , How to get a job there or how to communicate perfectly in the language of that place? and other questions. Despite these questions, all students who wish to study abroad hope that the experience in this country will be

worth it. Of course, this opens the door to a number of opportunities, however there are also disadvantages. If everyone learns all the pros and cons before planning to study abroad, it will make living there easier and help to make the right decisions. Now we will explore both the advantages and disadvantage of studying overseas.

These days, studying abroad brings people many advantages. Firstly, studying abroad helps to improve a person in many ways than studying at homeland. Such learning can improve language skills as we adjust to a new environment with new classes, homes and new friends. According to scientists, the best way to learn a foreign language is to live there and in that environment. For example, if the student is in countries such as America or England, learning English will not be a problem at all. Because they talk to people there and it boosts their confidence. Moreover, studying abroad is necessary for self-improvement and development due to the culture, traditions and lifestyle of the place of study. In addition, living in a new country increase confidence because we always try new things and face challenges from time to time. As a result, we lose our fear and overall confidence level increases enough to give us an edge in many other areas of their lives in the future. Besides, there are additional benefits of living abroad: 1 Experience a different teaching methods 2.Increased professional opportunities 3. Creating an independent lifestyle 4. Find new interests 5. Make new friend 6 life experience 7. It takes out of comfort zone 8. Brings a lot of change in mindset 9. take in new culture 10.Prestige and status

Studying abroad is a good option, however many universities are very expensive. According to Go Abroad, the average cost of studying abroad in foreign countries is \$18,000 for one semester and \$36,000 for a full academic year. But it does not guarantee a successful future for someone who has studied abroad. Finally, studying in another country can be dangerous and very difficult. A student's academic success can be affected by many problems such as weather, illness. A common problem for many students studying abroad is related to the

weather. The weather is something that no one can predict. If students don't have their own house to protect them, terrible storms can be very scary. Being abroad when a hurricane is coming can scare them, and they only have other students and their guardians for comfort. They should be prepared for such things, because unpleasant weather is a danger to them. Another example of dangerous study abroad problems is illness and medicine. When bad things happen, the place students are studying may not have the medical support system they need. Studying abroad is also uncomfortable for people for some reasons. First of all, culture shock is bound to happen when everyone is abroad. For the first time in foreign countries, they may see the behavior, speech, etc. of local people completely strange. It completely confuses and disturbs people. Therefore, when they experience culture shock, they can easily lose focus on studying. Second, people cannot avoid feeling homesick while studying abroad. This is because they have to live away from home in different habitats. In addition, they always have to solve problems themselves. All this makes them miss their families more than ever and reduces their enthusiasm for studying. Last but not least, people may have to study under pressure while abroad because of the huge amount of money they spend on studying abroad. They always have to worry about their grades in school for fear of not getting a good certificate. As a result, they can become stressed and their life abroad can turn into a nightmare.

In conclusion, there are advantages and disadvantages of going abroad to further your education. It is necessary to consider the advantages and disadvantages in every way and make a decision to study abroad. Obviously, many students overcome these handicaps, but what about others who can't handle all of them? Studying abroad may not be a good choice for all students. They should find this out before they leave their country. Otherwise, these problems will affect his whole life with failure. Studying abroad is a good option, but before the student leaves the country, it is necessary to carefully study its advantages and disadvantages.

Reference

1. KODIROVA, H. (2023). INGLIZ VA O‘ZBEK TILLARIDA SOXTA DISKURSNING PRAGMATIK PARAMETRLARI. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 29(29). извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/8920
2. KODIROVA, H. (2023). “MAVJUD PRAGMATIK KOMMUNIKATSIYA NAZARIYALARIDA “ALDOV/YOLG’ON“ NUTQIY AKTLARNING NAMOYON BO’LISHI”. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 29(29). извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/8919
3. KODIROVA, H. (2022). РЕЧЬ АКТ АНАЛИЗ ТЕЛЕГРАММНЫХ СООБЩЕНИЙ О КОРОНАВИРУСЕ: СОЦИАЛЬНЫЕ СЕТИ И ФЕЙКОВЫЕ НОВОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 8(8). извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/5986
4. KODIROVA, H. (2022). Факторы возникновения ложных дискурсивных актов в устной речи. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 8(8). извлечено от https://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/5985
5. Kodirova Kholida Khayriddin kizi. (2022). The Analysis of Illocutionary Acts in Adventures of Tom Sawyer by Mark Twain. Miasto Przyszłości, 28, 324–328. Retrieved from <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/648>
6. Kodirova, H. K., & Norova, D. (2022). THE ROLE OF THE BLENDED LEARNING IN TEACHING ESP STUDENTS. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON LEARNING AND TEACHING, 1(9), 235–238. Retrieved from <https://researchedu.org/index.php/iclt/article/view/1882>

7. Nargiza Bobojonova Jumaniyozovna. (2022). Categorization in Modern Linguistics. Miasto Przyszłości, 28, 351–356. Retrieved from <http://miastoprzyszlosci.com.pl/index.php/mp/article/view/653>

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1. studymoose.com
2. azent.com
3. topadvantasof.com
4. phdessay.com